

The Effect of Using the Canva Application on Learning Outcomes Art Culture Class Student VII Junior High School 2 Pancarijang

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine the effect of application usage Canva to Results Study Art Culture Student Class VII.1 SMPN 2 PANCARIJANG. Research This use method study quantitative with a random sampling research design with a posttest- only control group design Which aim For test Influence Use Application Canva to Results Study Art Culture Student Class VII.1 SMPN 2 Pancarijang. The population of this study were the 77 students of class VII.1 SMPN 2 with samples taken as many as 26 students of class VII.1 SMPN 2 and using random sampling technique. There are 2 variables in this study namely application usage Canva (independent variable) and Student Arts and Culture learning outcomes Class VII (dependent variable). Study this is implemented in class VII.1 Junior High School 2. Data collection techniques using documentation and tests. Results data The tests that have been collected are then analyzed using the mean and t-test formulas . Based on results analysis data, so obtained mark average group experiment = 83,461 And mark group control = 65,384 And on the t-test get T count 6,963 > from T table 5% (2,064) and 1% (2,797) with db 24. Based on the results of the study it can be concluded that the hypothesis (H 1) is states the Effect of Using the Canva Application on Art Learning Outcomes Culture Student Class VII.1 SMPN 2 PANCARIJANG "accepted".

INTRODUCTION

Education is a planned effort that aims to improve the quality and develop the potential of every human being. That matter in line with Law No. 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System which states that: education has an important role in the progress of a nation. Education must be able to accommodate learning activities so that later have ability in face change era. Learning an activity concept in which there is a teaching and learning process with demands that students master a number of learning (Wafiqni, et al., 2018). Education very important in prepare generation young face development era era technology. So that No eroded by development era, somebody demanded For take education, Good education Which its nature formal, education informal nor education non-formal (Nurmayanti et al., 2021) System education Now This Lots utilise technology To use to facilitate the work of educators and to improve quality students so that they can develop and get better results. According to Yuberti (2015), that other problems in education are decreased yields Study Which got by student. According to Supriyono (in Password 2020) "Quality student Which generated can said show success in the process Study Wrong only one seen from results Study Which achieved by student.

According to (Toto 2021) "learning outcomes are the formation of behavior from learning, there is a possibility of behavioral outcomes learn from what Which has studied. There are also those who, after learning, appear different behaviors new ie results accommodation Act in demand Which previously to information new moment learn (Sheila, 2022). According to Ulul (2015) argued that "problem Study is condition certain Which experienced by student so that it can impede the smooth process carried out by individuals in obtaining something a new and overall change in behavior ". Based on factors- factors that influence in improving student learning outcomes, one of them is media learning. Media learning Which too monotone will make para student only listen What which is being studied without understanding of the material presented by the teacher, there is also no activeness in learning. These learning problems can be overcome by changing media learning Which can attract attention (sheila, 2022).

Solutions to assist teachers in providing good learning outcomes more effective then learning media should be needed, because of information Which there is in media can involve student, Good in thought or mental as well as in the form of real activity, so that learning can be better. With the help of learning media materials can be designed in an appropriate manner more systematically and psychological, as well as can prepare instructions Study Which effective. In addition, learning media can provide experiences that are pleasant And fulfil need individual student, Because every student own ability Which different. Related with matter the, writer designing media learning use Application Canva . No only media learning, application This Also is an online design program that provides various tools or editing tools For make various design graphic like poster, flyer , infographic, banner, cardinvitation, presentation, facebook , cover And Still Lots Again. In addition, there are also

editing tools for photos, including photo editors, photo filters, photo frames, stickers, icon And design grids. Based on the background then the formulation of the problem in this study is "is there any effect of using the Canva application on learning outcomes Art Culture student class VII SMPN 2 Pancarijang?" Based on the formulation of the problem above, the purpose of this research is to find out whether there is an effect of using the Canva application on learning outcomes Art Culture class student VII SMPN 2 Pancarijang. In study This expected can give a number of benefit as following .

The results of this study can be used as deep reflection repair And reference use application Canva on learning Art Culture in SMPN 2 Pancarijang. Benefit practically Give addition reference method new learning Art Culture for school Support for progress knowledge knowledge And knowledge education onperiod Which will come. Help learning process and SMPN 2 student learning Pancarijang so that obtained results Which optimal.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In the Big Indonesian Dictionary, influence is the power that exists or arise from something (person, object) Which follow form character, belief, or someone's actions . Influence is something power or strength arises from something, be it people or things and everything that is in it natural so that influence anything Which are around (Mustafa, 2022). Influence is strength Which can arise from something object or person And Also symptom in Which can give change Which can form trust or change (Utami, 2013). Influence is Power Which cause something happened, inside meaning of something Which can form or change something else in a word other influence is reason something happen or can change something to form Which We want (Badudu, JS & Zain, 2001). According to WJS Poewardamita, influence is a Power Which exist in something whose nature can give change to which is its nature can give change to another (Munthe & Lubis, 2022). From a number of understanding according to para expert the so can concluded that influence is a power or strength that can arise from something, Good That character, person, object, trust And deed somebody Which can influence environment Which There is surrounding.

Learning is an effort made by someone (teacher or Which other) For learn student Which Study. On education formal (school), learning is a task assigned to the teacher, because Teacher is power professional Which be prepared For That (Calisom, 2021). Learning is something effort Which done educator or Teacher in a manner on purpose with objective convey knowledge knowledge, with method organize And create something system environment Study with various methods so that students can carry out learning activities optimally (Kiom, 2017).

Student learning outcomes are the abilities possessed by students Which obtained as results from experience Study. Ability the includes cognitive, affective and psychomotor aspects. Learning outcomes can be seen through evaluation activities aimed at obtaining evidentiary data Which will show level

ability student to achieve objective learning. On basically process learning is A business For bring and improve students in terms of behavior even more so from the side intellectual. Cultural arts is one of the subjects that is always there in every educational level which is inheritance from grandma ancestor Which loaded in curriculum school in order to preserve it. On period Now This development technology can utilized in the learning process to improve student learning outcomes. Besides than that the teacher can also use it as a more reference source Lots Again No only sourced from book just. Related to this, researchers want to know more deeply whether there is influence use Canva to results Study student on eye art lessons Culture.

METHODOLOGY

Approach Which used in study This is quantitative. According to (Sugiyono, 2013) method study quantitative is method scientific Because has fulfil rules scientific that is concrete, objective, measurable, rational And systematic. For get results from study This, especially formerly should make a design of the research that will be carried out. Research design what is being done is a true experimental design with a posttest- only control type group design . Following description implementation study This depicted in table simple following :

Table 1. Design Study

Group	Treatment
1 Experiment	X
2 Control	-

Information :

X : There is treatment on class experiment with use application Canva

- : No There is treatment on class control with use application Canva

Sample

The sample is part or representative of a population researched. According to (Sugiyono, 2013) the sample is a factor of the number of participants characteristics possessed by the population. Based on the opinion above, so sample Which used in study This that is Clusters Random sampling is do in a manner random to group, No towards the subject in a manner individual, random Also is taking with how to randomize the existing population and do not differentiate between one subject with Which other. Based on opinion in on, so sample Which used in This research, namely Cluster Random Sampling , is carried out randomly to group, No to subject in a manner individual, random Also is taking by randomizing the existing population and not differentiate between subject Which One with Which other. Sample from a population of 77 students in class XI SMP Negeri 2 Pancarijang In this study, researchers took a random sample, namely class VII.1 as much 26 student.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Study held on class VII in SMPN 2 Pancarijang. Class Which chosen as sample that is class VII.1 SMPN 2 Pancarijang . In This study was divided into 2 groups, namely the experimental group where in the process of learning activities will use the Canva application and groups control Where in activity Study No use application Canva. After carrying out the teaching and learning process of the two groups given test.

Presentation Data

From the results of research that has been done using documentation and test form essay as instrument collection data, so obtained results as following :

1. Data with variable X is data results Study Art Culture Which use application Canva (group experiment)
2. Data with variable Y is data results Study Art Culture Which No use application Canva (group control)

Table 2. Score and Mark Study Art Culture VII Group Experiment and Student Control Group Class VII SMPN 2 Pancarijang.

Code Sample	Score	Mark
AR	80	80
AF	85	85
AMR	85	85
AGH	80	80
AHD	75	75
DP	70	70
FH	80	80
FAZ	85	85
FTR	90	90
IAA	90	90
MAA	98	98
MFA	95	95
MFD	75	75

Source Data : Results test

Table 3. Score and Mark Results Group Control

Code Sample	Score	Mark
MQ	75	75
MYA	70	70
MRA	60	60
RA	65	65
RP	70	70
RA	70	70
hospital	65	65
SZI	65	65
TS	60	60
WI	65	65
YES	65	65
Y Y	60	60
YT	60	60

Source Data : Results test

DISCUSSION

Study This done with Meaning For know exists the effect of the Canva application on learning outcomes in the Cultural Arts subject class VII.1 SMPN 2 Pancarijang. Location implementation study This is at in VII.1 SMPN 2 Pancarijang by taking a sample of 36 students. In determine distribution group experiment And control by division based on number attendance. Based on acquisition mark Which obtained on study This shows the difference in learning outcomes of Cultural Arts class VII.1 students of SMPN 2 Pancarijang who uses the Canva application in the learning process is better compared to students who do the learning process as usual. Learning outcomes can be seen from the comparison of test scores that have been carried out on students in end process learning.

The results of the experimental group using the Canva application on the learning process obtained a higher score compared to the group controls that do not use the Canva application during the learning process. Matter the can seen from results acquisition analysis data Which done shows the average value of the experimental group ($M_x = 83.6923$) meanwhile control group ($M_y = 65.3846$). This value indicates that the value of M_x more big compared to my ($83,6923 > 65,3846$) And on test Independent sample t-test get T-test $6,991 >$ from Q table 5% (2,064) And 1% (2,797) with db 24 .Based on acquisition Which obtained on statement in on that hypothesis which states that there is an effect of using the Canva application on the results of learning Arts and Culture class VII.1 SMPN 2 Pancarijang "accepted" . Consequence reception the, so hypothesis Which state No There is the effect of using the Canva application on student learning outcomes in Cultural Arts class VII.1 SMPN 2 Pancarijang "rejected" .Thus it can be concluded that application usage Canva in the learning process can have a positive influence. This matter demonstrated by using the Canva application in the learning process of student learning

outcomes are quite satisfactory compared to the learning outcomes that are No using the app Canva on process Study.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of research on the effect of using the application Canva on the results of learning Arts and Culture class VII.1 students of SMPN2 Pancarijang can concluded as follows :Use application Canva on process Study teach give influence to results Study Art Culture student class VII.1 SMPN 2 Pancarijang. Matter This because use application Canva on process learning is more interesting and the information obtained is wider. Based on the results of this study that have been analyzed, then the average value is obtained $M_x = 83.6923 > M_y = 65.3846$ Independent sample t-test to get T- tests $6,991 >$ of Q table 5% (2,064) And 1% (2,797) with 24 db.

From results mark average Which found show exists influence usage application Canva to results Study Art Culture student class VII.1 SMPN 2 Pancarijang. Results end show that student Which Study use application Canva own impact Which positive compared to with students who study like usually. Expected can more role active in process Study teach especially in use application Canva so that activity Study more pull along information that obtained more Lots.Expected For can applied with use application Canvaa so that learning is more interesting and up-to-date so that the subject matter delivered with ok. got utilized as means help And support Teacher on process Study teach. Share study furthermore Results from study This expected can become material study For increase use deep application activity learning process teach.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations so further research needs to be done on this topic "The Effect of Using the Canva Application on Learning Outcomes Art Culture Class Student VII Junior High School 2 Pancarijang."

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